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Firms Characteristics And Earnings Management Practices Of Listed Non-Financial Firms In Nigeria

Rose Augustine Odokwo¹; Professor Nkanikpo Ibok² & Eno Gregory Ukpung³

^{1,3}Department of Accounting,
Faculty of Management Sciences
Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus, Nigeria

¹[mamarosey@yahoo.com/08029600703](mailto:mamarosey@yahoo.com)

³[enoukpong@aksu.edu.ng/08035016155](mailto:enoukpong@aksu.edu.ng)

²Department Marketing,
Faculty of Management Sciences
Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus, Nigeria

[nkanikpoibok@aksu.edu.ng/08106088451](mailto:nkanikpoibok@aksu.edu.ng)

ABSTRACT

The manipulation of financial reports to meet desired earnings targets is a pervasive issue in financial reporting. Financial scandals and the collapse of some multi-national corporations may be as a result of these earnings management practices, and the major determinants of these practices are firm characteristics. The main objective of this study therefore, was to examine the effect of firm characteristics on earnings management practices of non-financial firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group for the period 2014 to 2023. The research design adopted for this study was ex post facto. Secondary data were used and the population of the study was 109 listed non-financial firms in Nigeria and the sample size of 70 was purposively selected. The Robust regression technique was used in analysing the data and the statistical software employed was STATA 16. The results of the analysis revealed that managerial ownership has significant negative effect on real earnings management; audit quality has significant negative effect on real earnings management and financial leverage does not have significant effect on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. Based on these findings, it was thus concluded that firm characteristics have significant effect on earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. It was therefore recommended among others that top management of listed non-financial firms should own at least 20% of equity shares as a strategy to align the interests of managers with those of shareholders. It was also recommended that companies should invest in high-quality audit services to ensure rigorous financial oversight and compliance with accounting standards.

Keywords: Firm characteristic, earnings management, managerial ownership, audit quality, financial leverage.

INTRODUCTION

Financial statements are the mirror through which the investors gain insight into the efficiency of management and performance of the entity as a whole and it is a reliable instrument on which investors consider while making their investment decisions. Information on earnings is one of the crucial components in the financial statement. This is due to investors' belief that a firm which generates relatively good profits have good prospects and, thus, would expectedly provide optimal return to them (Tonye & Iganran, 2023). According to Adamu et al., (2022) Earnings management refers to the practice of intentionally manipulating a company's

financial results to meet certain financial targets or expectations. It is recognized as attempts by management to influence reported earnings by using specific accounting methods, accelerating expense or revenue transactions, or using other methods designed to influence short-term earnings (Enoitem et al., 2023). This characteristics or attributes reflect the identity, culture, values and reputation of the business and help distinguish it from competitors in the market place. Every company has its own vision, mission, goals, objectives, structure, features, strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats, work plans, and strategies, which distinguish it from other companies. According to Ibrahim et al. (2022), the characteristics of each sample company are clearly different with regard to their size, nature of business, capital structure, management style, quality of directors, corporate governance, ownership structure, business strategies, auditors' quality, customers, ethical culture, corporate social responsibility, corporate culture, ecological guidelines, market reputation, market capitalization, profitability and the like.

Thus, these characteristics such as managerial ownership, audit quality and financial leverage affect earnings management in one way or the other. Managerial ownership reflects the proportion of company shares held by top executives or key managers (Etim et al., 2023). High managerial ownership can align the interests of managers with those of other shareholders, potentially reducing the incentives for earnings manipulation. Conversely, low managerial ownership may raise concerns about agency conflicts and opportunistic behavior that could lead to earnings management practices. According to (Zehri & Shabou, 2021) audit quality represents the extent to which external auditors provide reliable and unbiased opinions on a company's financial statements. Strong audit quality can enhance the credibility and transparency of reported earnings, helping to deter manipulative practices. Higher audit quality, typically reflected by the reputation and independence of the auditing firm, can act as a deterrent to earnings management. A rigorous audit process may uncover attempts to manipulate earnings, leading to lower levels of earnings management. Conversely, poor audit quality may fail to detect or deter earnings management activities, undermining investor confidence and market efficiency (Abolo, 2022).

Financial leverage reflects the degree to which a firm relies on debt financing to support its operations and growth (Zhou & Habib (2020). Firms with higher financial leverage may have greater incentives to engage in earnings management to meet debt covenants or avoid default. High financial leverage can create pressure to report positive results, leading to higher levels of earnings management. On the other hand, firms with lower debt levels may have less pressure to manipulate earnings since they have fewer obligations to meet and potentially more stable financial health. Firm size refers to the scale or magnitude of a company which can be measured in terms of asset base, volume of sales, market capitalization and other relevant metrics (Etim et al., 2023). Firm size can influence a company's operations, strategy and impact on the market and economy. According to Bahaaeddin (2020) larger firms may face increased scrutiny from stakeholders and analysts, reducing the opportunity for excessive earnings management. Additionally, larger firms may have more resources and internal controls in place to mitigate the risk of earnings managements. This study was grounded on positive accounting theory (PAT) which was popularized by watts and Zimmerman in 1978. According to Watts and Zimmerman (1978), the positive accounting theory is based on the choices of accounting policies and responses made by a firm's management. These choices are a direct result of the management's desire to maximize their own utility. In exercising a choice of accounting policies, this theory posits that firms will choose those that best maximize benefits for the organization as a whole and not merely for shareholders. Thus, this study was undertaken to ascertain the effect of managerial ownership, audit quality and financial leverage, firms' size firms' age and firms' profitability on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. It is anticipated that the findings would specifically benefit to future researchers, management of companies, investors management and policy makers as this study would offer insights into the factors that influence a firm earning management practices and shed light on the potential risks and returns associated with different determinants of earnings management.

Statement of the problem

The act of earnings management, undertaken with the intention of presenting a favorable financial performance of a company that goes beyond its actual economic state, has been linked to instances of corporate financial scandals and catastrophes in contemporary times. This is possible by manipulating the application of Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) and other regulations. Firms' specific characteristics such as managerial ownership, audit quality, financial leverage and others are the major factors influencing earnings management practices. The literature reviewed showed that most of the studies on earnings management used

accrual methods in measuring earnings management. For instance, Rashwan et al. (2023); Chatterjee and Rakshit (2023); Abolo (2022), used discretionary accruals model. Also, most of the studies on firm characteristics and earnings management focused on other sectors of the economy such as non-financial firms (Amasiatu & Okoye, 2023); banking sector (Rashwan et al., 2023); Ibrahim et al. (2022); Adamu et al. (2022), oil and gas companies (Tonye & Iganran, 2023); consumer goods (George & Frank, 2023); construction companies (Abolo, 2022). It was thus as a result of these identified gaps that this study was carried out to ascertain the effect of firm characteristics on earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of firm characteristics on earnings management practices of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. Evaluate the effect of managerial ownership on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.
2. Examine the effect of audit quality on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.
3. Investigate the effect of financial leverage on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

Research questions

In order to achieve the above objectives, the following research questions were raised for the study;

1. What effect does managerial ownership have on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria?
2. What effect does audit quality have on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria?
3. What effect does financial leverage have on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria?

Research hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to help us answer the research questions;

- H₀₁: Managerial ownership does not have any significant effect on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₂: Audit quality does not have any significant effect on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₃: Financial leverage does not have any significant effect on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Firm characteristics

Firm characteristics refer to the attributes, qualities and features that describe a company or organization. This characteristics or attributes reflect the identity, culture, values and reputation of the business and help distinguish it from competitors in the market place. They can also be defined as the behavioral patterns of company's operation which enables them to achieve their objectives throughout the period of their operations. According to Etim et al (2023) firm characteristics can be defined as the wide varieties of information disclosed in the financial statement of business entities that serve as the predictors of the firm's quality of accounting information and performance. According to Mbonu and Amahalu (2021), firm characteristics are the various types of information presented in financial statements of business organizations that serve as predictors of the firms' accounting information quality and performance. According to Hasan (2021), the characteristics of each sample company are clearly different with regard to their size, nature of business, capital structure, management style, board independence, composition of board, quality of independent directors, corporate governance, ownership structure, business strategies, auditors quality, customers, access to financial services, leadership quality, innovation policy, entrepreneurship orientation, ethical culture, corporate social responsibility, corporate culture, ecological guidelines, market reputation, market capitalization, profitability and the like. This is also the same view as in Nkundabanyanga et al. (2020) who mentioned that firm characteristics distinguish one firm from another in terms of its functions and operations. According Aranda (2022) different firms have different strengths and weaknesses that affect the choice of competitive

strategy and firm characteristics are associated with resources, accumulation of experiences, and the nature of the business.

Managerial ownership

Managerial ownership refers to the ownership of company shares by the top managers or executives of the organization. Gordan (2018) viewed managerial shareholding as the percentage of ordinary shares owned by the directors, executive directors and independent directors. Ruan et al. (2022) viewed managerial shareholding as the proportion of managers' stock ownership. Laiho (2019) described managerial shareholding as the insider holdings by the board of directors and the management team. Jensen & Meckling (1976) defined managerial ownership as the fraction of the firm's shares held by its manager. The proportion of management shareholders that actively participate in corporate decision making by directors and commissioners is referred to as ownership management (Diyah & Widanar, 2009). Managerial ownership is expressed through a number of ownership shares owned by management and the board of commissioners divided by the total shares of the company (Masdupi, 2005). Managers with significant ownership may be motivated to meet or exceed earnings forecasts, Managers with substantial ownership stakes have a vested interest in maintaining the integrity and transparency of financial reporting, as their wealth is linked to the firm's enduring performance and reputation boost dividends, or maintain stock price stability, as these factors directly impact their wealth. Gul et al. (2023); Jung and Kwon (2022); Aygun et al. (2014); Ogbonnaya et al. (2016) found that increased managerial ownership would increase earnings management practices; suggesting a positive relationship between them. While Ali et al. (2020); Banderlipe (2019) and Euphrasia and Dini (2020) found that the relationship between managerial ownership and earnings management depends on firm size.

Audit quality

According to Christensen et al. (2016), audit quality refers to the extent to which users of financial statements can depend on an audit opinion. Audit quality may be defined as "the market-assessed joint probability that an auditor will discover misstatement in the client's accounting system, and report the misstatement" (DeAngelo (1981). Stated differently, it refers to the auditors' integrity and objectivity in identifying and revealing material misstatements. It is significant to remember that an auditor's likelihood of finding a misstatement indicates their level of knowledge and ability, whereas their likelihood of reporting the misstatement indicates their degree of independence (Harris & Williams, 2020). The expertise and experience of the personnel conducting the audit is the first of three elements that Kouaib and Jarboui (2014) identified as enhancing audit quality. High-quality audits, typically provided by reputable and larger audit firms, are more likely to detect and deter earnings management. These auditors are thorough and adhere to stringent standards, making it difficult for firms to manipulate earnings without detection (Tonye & Iganran, 2023). Gul et al. (2023), Ching et al. (2015), and Nwoye et al. (2021) all found a positive relationship between audit tenure and earnings management. On the contrary Zhou and Elder (2020), and Tendeloo and Vanstraelen (2019), found a negative relationship between auditor type and earnings management.

Financial leverage

Basically, financial leverage refers to the degree to which a firm's capital structure comprises more of long-term debt as against equity. Financial leverage refers to the use of borrowed funds (such as loans or bonds) to finance investments and operations in a company. It involves using debt or other financial instruments to increase the potential return on investment or earnings for shareholders (Chindengwike, 2024). In essence, financial leverage allows a company to use borrowed money to generate higher returns than the cost of borrowing. The firm leverage indicates the level of indebtedness of the business, which refers to the degree of financial risks that are faced by the business. Firm leverage refers to the extent to which a company has borrowed funds from external sources to finance its operations and growth. It is measured by the ratio of total debt to total assets of a company (George & Frank, 2023). It is important to note that leverage in any firm depends on many factors. A factor that can affect a company's leverage is its profitability. Companies with higher profits may be more likely to use debt financing to take advantage of tax benefits and to invest in growth opportunities (Lang & Lundholm, 2019). Conversely, companies with lower profits may be more cautious about taking on debt, as they may have more difficulty making interest payments and servicing their debt obligations (Myers, 1984). A company's liquidity can also influence its leverage. Companies with high levels of financial leverage (i.e., high debt-to-equity ratios) may face pressure to manage earnings to meet debt covenants, avoid default, or maintain credit ratings (Setyoputri & Mardijuwono, 2020). Almalita (2017)

suggested a positive relationship between leverage and earnings management, while Astuti (2017) however, found that leverage had no influence on earnings management.

Earnings management (EM)

Earnings management refers to the practice of intentionally manipulating a company's financial results to meet certain financial targets or expectations (Ujah & Brusa, 2021). Earnings management is recognized as attempts by management to influence reported earnings by using specific accounting methods, accelerating expense or revenue transactions, or using other methods designed to influence short-term earnings (Uwa, 2021). According to Akpan et al. (2022) earning management remains an important issue that has come to the front burner in recent debate on corporate failures regarding unethical behaviour (Uwuigbe et al., 2015). While not all forms of earnings management are illegal, they can raise ethical concerns and mislead investors and other shareholders about a company's true financial performance. The term 'earnings management' embodies a wide array of accounting techniques used by management to achieve a specific earnings objective. Earnings management is called by several names such as accounting numbers game (Mulford & Comiskey, 2002) creative accounting (Balaciu et al., 2009), income smoothing (Tucker & Zarowin, 2006), and so on. Real earnings management is a manipulation done by the company management through the company's operational activities that directly impact the company's cash flow (Sun & Lan, 2014). It occurs when managers intentionally make operational decisions that have actual cash flow implications with a view to altering reported earnings.

Theoretical Framework

The major theory supporting this study was agency theory as developed by Jensen and Meckling (1976). This theory focuses primarily on associations involving two distinct groups of people: the owner, who serves as the principal, and the agent, who acts on the owner's behalf (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). According to the theory, when given the freedom to act, agents frequently act in their own interests without giving adequate thought to the interests of the principal (Jensen & Meckling). As a result, some operational elements are put in place to monitor and manage the actions of agents as well as to bridge the conflict of interest between the two parties (Fama & Jensen, 1983). According to Uwa (2022), in order to maximize shareholders' long-term wealth and deter short-term executive manipulations that harm an organization, other related arrangements link executive compensation with the benefits of shareholders and also extend a portion of executive compensation into the future. According to the agency theory, there are two ways to lessen agency issues while still controlling agents' self-interest (Eisenhardt, 1989). The first choice is to establish a governance system that aids in monitoring and regulating the actual manager activities. The establishment of a governance system that is based on the actual outcomes of manager behavior is the other aspect (Eisenhardt, 1989). Risks are therefore transferred to the managers, creating a motivation to close the conflict of interest between managers and shareholders.

Agency theory supports this study because firm characteristics such as ownership structure and audit quality can impact agency cost. For instance, firms with low or no managerial ownership may face higher agency cost. Also, this theory also suggests the importance of monitoring mechanism (effective audit) to mitigate agency problem and reduce the likelihood of earnings management. Monitoring mechanism such as external audit help enhance transparency and accountability in financial reporting. Firm characteristics that facilitate effective monitoring such as managerial shareholding can act as a deterrent to earnings management.

Empirical Reviews

A good number of studies have been carried out on the effect of firms' characteristics on earnings management over the last few decades in both developed and developing economies. The studies employed different methodologies and have produced different findings, resulting in divergent opinions regarding the effect of firm characteristics on earnings management. Rajpurohit and Rijwani (2024) examined the impact of firm characteristics on earnings management (EM) using a sample of listed non-financial firms in India. The research focused on firm characteristics such as size, leverage, performance, growth opportunities, and industry membership, which are hypothesized to influence accruals EM. The findings indicated that large firms and those with high performance exhibited higher accruals quality; firms with greater growth opportunities tended to have lower accruals quality; firms with high leverage used accruals EM as a strategy to avoid breaching debt covenants. Chatterjee and Rakshit (2023) conducted an evaluation of the relationship

between different corporate governance mechanisms and earnings management measured using discretionary accruals. The study utilized panel data regression and Fisher's probability test. They found a robust inverse correlation between earnings management and both the proportion of autonomous directors serving on the board and the conscientiousness of board members.

Enoidem et al., (2023) examined the effect of board monitoring mechanisms on earnings managements of non-finance firms listed on the floor of the Nigeria Exchange Group from 2012-2021. Least square variable regression was adopted to analyze and test the three hypotheses formulated for the study. The study revealed that board size, board independence, board gender diversity has significant negative effect on earnings management of non-finance firms listed on the floor of the Nigeria Exchange Group. Tonye and Iganran (2023) investigated the determinants of earnings management practises of publicly traded Nigerian oil and gas enterprises. A correlational study method was employed to establish the association among the specified predictors of management of earnings. The outcome of the analysis implied that there exists a negative and substantial association between external auditor's attribute and earnings management of listed petroleum firms in Nigeria and both external sector specialization and audit committee gender. George and Frank (2023) investigated the determinants of earnings management among quoted industrial and consumer goods sectors in Nigeria between the periods of 2012-2022. The findings revealed that share price and return on assets are the primary determinants that significantly affect the earnings management of publicly traded companies in the industrial and consumer goods sectors during the observed timeframe.

Etim et al. (2023) examined the influence of the firm's characteristics on asset growth of quoted companies in Nigerisa. The findings revealed an insignificant influence of firm characteristics (profitability, leverage and revenue growth) on asset growth of quoted companies in Nigeria. Rashwan et al. (2023) investigated the impact of earning management on dividend payout, while also examining the moderating influence of financial leverage on this association. The study found a correlation between earning management and dividend payout in the banking industry of Palestine and Jordan. Similarly, Amasiatu and Okoye (2023) assessed the effect of corporate attributes on earnings management of non-financial firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). Empirically, the results revealed that both company size and company age have significant effect on earnings management of non-financial firms in Nigeria as measured using modified Jones Model. Abolo (2022) examined earnings management and the quality of financial reporting of listed construction companies in Nigeria. The findings of the study were that; there is a positive and significant relationship between accrual earnings and faithful representation of construction companies in Nigeria. Ibrahim et al. (2022) examined the effect of firm attributes on earnings management of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study found that firm size and leverage have significant negative relationship with earnings management of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria while profitability and liquidity insignificant negative relationship with earnings quality with DMBs in Nigeria.

Akpan et al. (2022) evaluated the moderating effect of audit committee, gender diversity on the relationship between social responsibility disclosure and earnings management of selected consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The results showed that audit committee gender diversity significantly moderate the relationship between social donation disclosure and earnings management. The results also showed that audit committee gender diversity significantly moderates the relationship between employee disclosure and earnings management. Adamu et al. (2022) examined the relationship between board attributes and real earnings management of listed Nigerian financial institutions. The residuals from Roychowdhury (2006) were used to proxy real earnings management. The regression result showed that board meeting and board expertise have a significant positive impact on real earnings management. Whereas, female directors have a significant negative influence on real earnings management.

METHODOLOGY

Ex-post facto research design was used in this study. This design was suitable for this study because historical data was used. The population of this study consisted of 109 non-financial firms listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group from 2014-2023. The sample size for this study was 70 companies and purposive sampling technique was employed. Secondary data source was employed to generate the data for analysis robust regression analysis was used in analysing the study.

Model specification

The model used in this study was adapted from the study of Ibrahim et al., (2022) and was modified to fit this study as presented below;

$$REM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MOWN_{it} + \beta_2 AUDQ_{it} + \beta_3 FLEV_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where:

REM	=	Real earnings management
MOWN	=	Managerial ownership
AUDQ	=	Audit quality
FLEV	=	Financial leverage
β_0	=	Model intercept
β_1, β_3	=	Coefficient to be estimated
it	=	Cross section of listed consumer goods firms with time variant
ϵ_{it}	=	Stochastic error term

Measurement of variables

This section gives the measurement of the variables used in this study which are given below;

Independent variable

The independent variable of this study was firms’ characteristics and this was proxied by managerial ownership, audit quality and financial leverage and the were measured as given below.

Managerial ownership: This was measured as the ratio of number of shares held by top management of the company to the total share capital of the company and the result was multiplied by 100.

Audit quality: This was measured using dummy variables and “1” was assign where the company was audited by the Big Four audit firms and “0” where the firm was audited by any other firms of external auditors

Financial leverage: This was measured as the ratio of long-term loans to the long-term funds of the entity. Long term fund is the sum of long-term loans and total shareholders’ fund and the result was multiplied by 100.

Dependent variable

The dependent variable of this study was earnings management and this was proxied by real earnings management.

Real earnings management

Real earnings management was measured using the aggregate of three items following the model provided by Roychowdhury (2006) and this include abnormal levels of cash flows from operations, production costs and discretionary expenses. This method was also used in similar studies including those of George and Frank (2023), Adamu et al. (2022) and Nkiru et al. (2019).

Thus the study applied the model Roychowdhury, (2006) to compute normal level of cash flows from operations as given below;

$$CFO_{it}/A_{it-1} = \beta_1(1/A_{it-1}) + \beta_2 (Sales_{it} / A_{it-1}) + \beta_3 (\Delta Sales_{it} / A_{it-1}) + \epsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where:

CFO_{it}	=	Cash flows from operations of firm i in period t;
A_{it-1}	=	Total assets of firm i in year t-1;(total assets of the previous year)
$Sales_{it}$	=	Sales of firm i in year t;
$\Delta Sales_{it}$	=	Sales of firm i in year t less sales of firm i in year t-1; (Current year sale less previous year sale)
ϵ_{it}	=	A residual term that captures the level of abnormal cash flows of firm i in year t;
$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$	=	are firm specific parameters.

The normal level of discretionary expenses is as follows:

$$DISCEXP_{it} / A_{it-1} = \beta_1(1/A_{it-1}) + \beta_2 (Sales_{it-1} / A_{it-1}) + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where:

$DISEXP_{i,t}$	=	The sum of selling and marketing expenses and general and administrative (expenses) = of firm i in year t;
A_{it-1}	=	Total assets of firm i in year t-1
$Sales_{it-1}$	=	Sales of firm i in year t-1

ϵ_{it} = A residual term that captures the level of abnormal discretionary expenses of firm i in year t ;

β_1, β_2 = are firm specific parameters.

The normal level of production cost is as follows:

$$PROD_{it} / A_{t-1} = \beta_1 (1/A_{t-1}) + \beta_2 (Sales_{i,t-1} / A_{t-1}) + \beta_3 (\Delta Sales_{i,t} / A_{t-1}) + \beta_4 (\Delta Sales_{i,t-1} / A_{t-1}) \epsilon_{it} \tag{3}$$

Where:

$PROD_{it}$ = The sum of cost of goods sold and change in inventory of firm i in year t ;

A_{it-1} = Total assets of firm i in year $t-1$;

$Sales_{it}$ = Sales of firm i in year t ;

$\Delta Sales_{it}$ = Sales of firm i in year t less sales of firm i in year $t-1$;

$\Delta Sales_{it-1}$ = Sales of firm i in year $t-1$ less sales of firm i in year $t-2$;

ϵ_{it} = A residual term that captures the level of abnormal production costs of firm i in year t ;

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = firm specific parameters.

Thus, real earnings management (REM) =

Abnormal levels of cash flows from operations + Abnormal level of cash flows from production costs + Abnormal cash flows from discretionary expenses.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Descriptive Analyses

Table 4.1: Descriptive statistics of the effect of firm characteristics and earnings management

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Rem	700	-1.931	2.351	-25.170	13.110
Mown	700	21.885	27.364	0.000	89.650
Audq	700	0.534	0.499	0.000	1.000
Flev	700	68.200	46.170	1.610	395.450

Source: Authors Computation (2024)

Table 4.1 presents descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study. Real earnings management (REM), shows a mean of -1.931 with a standard deviation of 2.351, indicating a negative skewness in real earnings management practices. Managerial ownership (MOWN), representing managerial ownership, has a mean of 21.885% and a high standard deviation of 27.364, indicating a diverse ownership structure across firms. Audit quality (AUDQ), with a mean of 0.534 and a standard deviation of 0.499, suggests that slightly more than half of the firms engage high-quality auditors, reflecting moderate attention to audit quality. Financial leverage (FLEV) shows significant dispersion with a mean of 68% and a standard deviation of 46.170, This indicates that while some firms are minimally leveraged, others carry substantial debt, impacting their financial structures and risk profiles.

Correlation analysis

Table 4.2: Correlation analyses of the association between firms' characteristics and earnings management

Variables	REM	MOWN	AUDQ	FLEV
REV	1.000			
MOWN	0.043	1.000		
AUDQ	-0.255	-0.382	1.000	
FLEV	0.052	0.108	-0.026	1.000

Source: Authors computation (2024)

In the case of the correlation between managerial ownership, audit quality, financial leverage and real earnings management (REM), table 4.2 shows that there exists a positive association between managerial ownership (0.043) and real earnings management (REM) during the period under study. The result shows that there is a negative association between of audit quality (-0.255) and REM during the period under study. The results also indicate that there is a positive association between financial leverage (0.052) real earnings management (REM) during the period under study. The associations were seen to be weak and there is no room to suspect the presence of multicollinearity

Regression analysis

Table 4.3: Regression analysis of the effect of firms' characteristics on earnings management

Variables	(1) OLS-REM	(2) Robust-REM
mown	-0.015*** (0.000)	-0.007*** (0.000)
audq	-0.777*** (0.000)	-0.458*** (0.000)
flev	0.000 (0.920)	-0.001 (0.522)
Intercept	1.315 (0.101)	0.638 (0.141)
Observations	700	700
R ²	0.121	0.297
Hetest	56.63{0.000}	
VIF	1.19	

Notes: p-values are in parentheses. *** p<.01, ** p<.05

Source: Authors Computation (2024)

The result obtained from the robust regression analyses is presented in the table 4.3. The result indicates that the OLS regression had an R-squared value of 0.121. This implies that the independent variables of the study could explain about 12.1% of the systematic changes in the dependent variable of real earnings management (REM) during the period under study. However, the unexplained part of real earnings management has been captured by the error term. The result of the F-statistics of the OLS regression model for the sample firms in Nigeria with the associated p-value indicates that the OLS regression model, on the overall, is statistically fit and can be employed for statistical inferences. However, to further validate the estimates of the OLS results, this study also tests multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity.

Test for multicollinearity

The data presented in Table 4.3 shows that the average VIF is 1.19. Given that the mean VIF is less than 10 (Greene, 2009), this suggests that there is no multicollinearity and further supports the idea that none of the independent variables should be removed from the model.

Test for heteroscedasticity

The result of the heteroscedasticity test in table 4.3 shows a chi2 value of 56.63 with a p-value of 0.000. The result shows significant p-values indicating that the assumption of homoscedasticity of the OLS regression results has been violated. Hence, the study re-specifies the model to control for this violation by employing robust regression as recommended by Greene (2009).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Managerial ownership and real earnings management

The results obtained from the Robust regression model in table 4.3 revealed that managerial ownership [coef. = -0.007 (0.000)] has a significant negative effect on the real earnings management during the period under study. This indicates that when managers align their interests with shareholders by owning significant financial stake in the company, they may be more motivated to act in ways that protect and enhance the firm's long-term value rather than pursuing short-term gains through earnings manipulation. This alignment could foster a more transparent and accurate reporting environment, ultimately benefiting the firm's credibility and investor

confidence. This outcome is consistent with the results reported by Chatterjee and Rakshit (2023) and Rashwan et al. (2023), who also observed that higher managerial ownership is associated with reduced earnings management, as managers with significant ownership stakes are less likely to engage in practices that could harm the firm's reputation or financial stability. However, George and Frank (2023) argue that in some contexts, managerial ownership does not significantly influence earnings management behaviours.

Audit quality and real earnings management

The results obtained from the Robust regression model in table 4.3 revealed that managerial ownership [coef. = -0.458 (0.000)] has a significant negative effect on the real earnings management during the period under study. This outcome suggests that firms with higher-quality audits are less likely to engage in real earnings management practices, as rigorous and thorough audits are more likely to detect and prevent such manipulations. This result highlights the critical role of audit quality in enhancing financial reporting accuracy and protecting stakeholders' interests, thus fostering a transparent corporate environment. This aligns with the findings of Rajpurohit and Rijwani (2024), who also reported that high audit quality effectively mitigates earnings management, as it enhances the reliability and credibility of financial information. Similarly, Abolo (2022) found that stringent audit processes reduce the opportunities for management to engage in earnings manipulation, thereby promoting more accurate and fair representation of a company's financial performance.

Financial leverage and real earnings management

The results obtained from the Robust regression model in table 4.3 revealed that managerial ownership [coef. = -0.001 (0.522)] does not have significant effect on the real earnings management during the period under study. This indicates that other factors, potentially including managerial motivations, corporate governance mechanisms, or external economic conditions, might play a more crucial role in determining earnings management behaviors than the degree of financial leverage. This findings agree with the submission of Amasiatu and Okoye (2023) who found that the mere presence of financial leverage does not consistently lead to earnings management. They noted that companies may utilize a variety of methods to meet financial targets, regardless of their leverage situation. In contrast, this finding differs from the research of Amasiatu and Okoye (2023) who observed a positive correlation between financial leverage and earnings management, particularly in firms experiencing financial difficulties. They argued that companies with high levels of debt might resort to manipulating earnings to enhance financial ratios and satisfy creditors. Additionally, Abolo (2022) noted that the influence of financial leverage on earnings management could vary depending on a firm's access to external financing.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study sought to understand how specific firm characteristics influence real earnings management practices among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. Real earnings management, a subtle form of earnings manipulation, can have significant implications for financial transparency and investor confidence. Based on the findings the significant findings of this study, it was concluded that firm specific characteristics such managerial ownership, audit quality and financial leverage can influence the earnings management practices of non-financial firms. Therefore, it was recommended that top management of listed non-financial firms should own at least 20% of equity shares as a strategy to align the interests of managers with those of shareholders. They should only engage the services of the “Big 4” audit firms since they are better equipped to detect earnings management practices and provide assurance on the accuracy and reliability of financial reporting for the clients.

REFERENCES

- Abolo, A. P. (2022). Earnings management and quality of financial reporting of listed construction companies in Nigeria. *BW Academic Journal*, 1(1), 16-26.
- Adamu, E., Diri, M., Lambrinouidakis, C., & Alhadab, M. (2022). Corporate governance and earnings management in concentrated market. *Journal of Business Research*, 108, 291-306.
- Akpan, D. C., Simeon, U. J., & Nkpodot, U. K. (2022). Audit committee gender diversity, CSR and earnings management of selected consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *AKSU Journal of Administration and Governance*, 2(2), 1-14.

- Ali, S. M., Salleh, N. M., & Hassan, M. S. (2020). Ownership structure and earnings management in Malaysian listed companies: the size effect. *Asian Journal of Business and Accounting*, 1(2), 109-123
- Amasiatu, K. M., & Okoye E. I. (2023). Corporate attributes and earnings management of non-financial firms listed on the Nigeria Exchange Limited. *Journal of Global Accounting*, 9(3), 134-154.
- Aqabna, S. M., Aga, M., & Jabari, H. N. (2023). Firm performance, corporate social responsibility and the impact of earnings management during COVID-19: Evidence from MENA Region. *Sustainability*, 15(2), 1485.
- Aranda, A. D. (2022). Relationship between operations strategy and size in engineering consulting firms. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 13, 263–85.
- Astuti, A. Y., Nuraina, E., & Wijaya, A. L. (2017). Pengaruh ukuran perusahaan dan leverage terhadap manajemen laba. *The 9th FIPA: Forum Ilmiah Pendidikan Akuntansi*, 5(1), 501–514.
- Aygun, M. Suleyman, I. C., & Sayim, M. (2014). The effects of corporate ownership structure and board size on earnings management: Evidence from Turkey. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 9(12), 123-132.
- Bahaaeddin, A. (2020). The impact of firm-specific characteristics on earnings management: evidence from GCC countries. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 10(3). 1 - 20.
- Balaciu, D., Bogdan, V., & Vladu, A. B. (2009). A brief review of creative accounting literature and its consequences in practice. *Annales Universitatis Apulensis Series Oeconomica*, 11(1), 170–82.
- Banderlipe, M. R. (2019). The impact of selected corporate governance variables in mitigating earnings management in the Philippines. *DLSU Business & Economics Review*, 19(1), 17–27.
- Chatterjee, R., & Rakshit, D. (2023). Association between earnings management and corporate governance mechanisms: A study based on select firms in India. *Global Business Review*, 24(1), 152-170.
- Chindengwike, J. D. (2024). Nexus between financial leverage and dividend payout from manufacturing firms listed at Dar es Salaam stock exchange, Tanzania. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1), 22-34
- Ching, C. P., Teh, B. H., & San, O. T. (2015). The relationship among audit quality, earnings management, and financial performance of Malaysian public listed companies. *International Journal of Economics and Management*, 9(1), 211-229.
- Christensen, B. E., Glover, S. M., Omer, T. C., & Shelley, M. K. (2016). Understanding audit quality: Insights from audit professionals and investors. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 33(4), 1648-1684.
- Cornett, M. M., Marcus, A. J., & Tehranian, H. (2020). Corporate governance and pay-for-performance: The impact of earnings management. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 87, 357-373.
- DeAngelo, L. E. (1981). Auditor size and audit quality. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 3(3), 183-199.
- Diyah, P., & Widanar, E. (2009). Influence to company value: Financial decision as intervening variable. *Journal of Business Economics and Venture Accounting*, 12(1), 71-86.
- Fama, E. F., & Jensen, M. C. (1983). Separation of ownership and control. *Journal of Law and Economics*, 26, 301- 325.
- Eisendhart, K. M. (1989). Building theories from case study research. *Academy of Management Review*, 14, 532-550.
- Etim, O. E., Ekpoese, J. D., Akporien, O. F., & Akpan, D. C. (2023). Firms' characteristics and asset growth of quoted companies in Nigeria: An Analytical Approach. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 1(9), 16-22.
- Euphrasia, S. S., & Dini, D. T. (2020). The influence of corporate governance mechanism on earnings management of Indonesia and China industrial banks. *International Conference on Eurasian Economics*, 144-150.
- Harris, M. K., & Williams, L. T. (2020). Audit quality indicators: Perspectives from Non-Big Four audit firms and small company audit committees. *Advances in Accounting*, 50, 100-114.
- Hasan, K. (2021). The association between firm-specific characteristics and disclosure: Evidence from the Johannesburg Stock Exchange. *Meditari Accountancy Research*, 17(1), 19-37.
- Healy, P. M., & Wahlen, J. (1999). A review of the earnings management literature and its implications for standard setting. *Accounting Horizons*, 13(4), 365-384.
- George, O., & Frank, E. (2023). An assessment of the determinants of earnings management in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*, 5(9), 681-694.

- Gordan, K. (2018). Equity ownership structure, risk taking, and performance. *Emerging Markets, Finance & Trade*, 38(6), 6-16.
- Greene, W. H. (2003) *Econometric Analysis*. 5th Edition, Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River.
- Gul, F. A., Fung, Y. K. S., & Bikki, J. (2023). Earnings quality: Some evidence on the role of auditor tenure and auditors' industry expertise. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 47, 265-287.
- Ibrahim, J., Adebayo, Olowookere, K., & Oladejo, T. (2023). Firm structural attributes and capital structure adjustments among listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria using static and dynamic approaches. *FUDMA Journal of Accounting and Finance Research*. 1(3) 52-63.
- Isenmila, P. A., & Afensimi, E. (2012). Earnings management and ownership structure: Evidence from Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 3(7), 24-36.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behaviour, agency costs and ownership Structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305-360.
- Jung, K., & Soo Kwo, Y. (2022). Ownership structure and earnings informativeness: Evidence from Korea. *The International Journal of Accounting*, 37(3), 301-325.
- Kouaib, A., & Jarboui, A. (2014). External audit quality and ownership structure: Interaction and impact on earnings management of industrial and commercial Tunisian sectors. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 19(37), 78-89.
- Laiho, T. (2019). Agency theory and ownership structure-estimating the effect of ownership structure on firm performance. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 5(3), 73-92.
- Lang, M. H., & Lundholm, R. J. (2019). Cross-sectional determinants of analyst ratings of corporate disclosures. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 31(2), 246-271.
- Masdupi, E. (2005). Analysis of the impact of ownership structure on debt policy in controlling agency conflict. *Journal of Economics and Business of Indonesia*, 20(1), 57-69.
- Mbonu, C. M., & Amahalu, N. N. (2021). Effect of firm characteristics on capital structure of insurance companies listed on Nigeria stock exchange. *International Journal of Management Studies and Social Science Research*, 3(5), 217-228.
- Mulford, C. W., & Comiskey, E. E. (2002). The financial numbers game: Detecting creative accounting practices on earnings management. *Business and Economy*. 20(1), 61-68.
- Myers, S. C. (1984). *Capital structure puzzle*. Pitman press.
- Nkiru P. O., Godwin O. & John E. (2019). Firm-specific attributes and earnings management of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. *International Conferene on Accounting, Finance and Insurance – ICAIF*, 89-108.
- Nkundabanyanga, S. K., Mugumya, E., Nalukenge, I., Muhwezi, M., & Najjemba, G. M. (2020). Firm characteristics, innovation, financial resilience and survival of financial institutions. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 10(1), 48-73.
- Nwoye, C. M., Anichebe, A. S., & Osegbue, I. F. (2021). Effect of audit quality on earnings management in insurance companies in Nigeria. *Athens Journal of Business & Economics*, 7(2), 173-202.
- Ogbonnaya, A., Chidiebere, E. M., & Ihendinihu, J. (2016). Effect of corporate governance and ownership structure on earnings management Of brewery industry. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 4(7), 35-45.
- Orbunde, B., Oyewobi, I., & Musa, U. F. (2021). Effect of audit quality on earnings management of listed oil and gas marketing companies in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 1(2), 54-67.
- Rajpurohit, P., & Rijwani, P. (2024). The impact of firm characteristics on earnings management: A study of firms listed in India. *Journal of Commerce & Accounting Research*, 13(2), 66-73.
- Rashwan, A. R. M., Yousef Shaker Melhem, A., Nour, A. I., & Atout, S. (2023). The effect of earning management on dividend payouts and the mediating role of financial leverage. *Economics Times*, 22(1), 7-17.
- Roychowdhury, S. (2006). Earnings management through real activities manipulation. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 42, 335-370.
- Ruan, K., Tian, L., & Ma, K. (2022). Corporate ownership structure and firm performance: Evidence from Greek firms. Bank of Greece Economic Research Department – Special Studies Division. Working Paper.

- Setyoputri, L. S., & Mardijuwono, A. W. (2020). The impact of firm attributes on earnings management. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 22(1), 90-108.
- Shadrach, M., & Yakura, P. I. (2021). The effect of firm characteristics and earnings management in deposit money bank. *Fuoye Journal of Accounting and Management*, 1(1), 89-99.
- Sun, J., & Lan, G. (2014). Independent audit committee characteristics and real earnings management. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 29(2), 153-172.
- Tendeloo, B., & Vanstraelen, A. (2019). Earnings management and audit quality in Europe: Evidence from the private client segment market. *European Accounting Review*, 3, 447–469.
- Tonye, O., & Iganran W. (2023). Determinants of earnings management of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Management Studies*, 10(6), 67-74.
- Trisnawati, R. (2012). The real earnings management practices (The comparative studies between shariah index (JII) and conventional index (LQ-45) in Indonesian stock exchange during 2004-2010 period). *Accounting Perspectives*, 2(1), 20-34.
- Tucker, J. W., & Zarowin, P. A. (2006). Does income smoothing improve earnings informativeness? *The Accounting Review*, 81(1), 251- 270.
- Ujah, N., & Brusa, J. (2021). Earnings management, financial leverage, and cash flow volatility: Do economic conditions matter? *Journal of Global Accounting Technology*, 2(3), 67-74.
- Uwa, K. L. (2021). Multivariate analysis of the factors that influence strategic management practices among commercial banks in Uyo. *European Journal of business and innovation research*
- Uwa, K. L. (2022). Organizational fairness and organizational behaviour : A study of fast food industries in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 10(2), 33-43.
- Uwuigbe, U., Uwuigbe, O. R., & Okorie, B. (2015). Assessment of the effects of firms characteristics on earnings management of listed firms in Nigeria. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 5(2), 218-228.
- Zhou, J., & Elder, R. (2020). Audit quality and earnings management by seasoned equity offering firms. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Accounting & Economics*, 11(2), 95-120.
- Zhou, D., & Habib, A. (2020). Accounting standards and earnings management: Evidence from China', *Accounting Perspectives*, 12(3), 213-236.
- Zehri, F., & Shabou, R. (2021). Audit quality, corporate governance and earnings management in the context of Tunisian firms. *Journal of Administrative & Economics Science*, 1(1), 40-59.